

Exploiting depth features for picking objects in cluttered environments

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Abstract—This work presents a commercial collaborative robot that integrates a classical two-finger gripper and a custom-designed Universal Jamming Gripper (UJG). To exploit at best the potentialities of the UJG 3D perception technologies are employed for selecting suitable geometries for picking objects of different shapes. The proposed system is competitive in terms of grasping success rate with respect to two state-of-the-art systems and outperforms them in the searching time of the grasping point.

Index Terms—Autonomous Picking, Universal Jamming Gripper, Computer Vision, Collaborative Robotics, Baxter, ROS, Kinect v2

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotics solutions in the industrial sector are moving towards higher degrees of flexibility. The challenge of developing flexible solutions where production lines can be quickly re-planned, adapted, and structured for new or slightly changed products is an important open problem. Industrial robots today are still largely pre-programmed for their tasks and are not able to adapt their behavior in the complexity of the industrial environment. But in the next future, humans and robots will share the same workspace and will perform different object manipulation tasks in a collaborative manner.

Nowadays, one of the most repetitive tasks for human workers is picking and place of objects. The latest researches are focused on vision systems and grasping technologies for material handling for automating such a task. This work aims to study a possible way to overcome current limitations on the existing robotic solutions for picking objects in cluttered environments.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

This work presents a collaborative robotics system that uses the Baxter robot as cobotic platform. It integrates a classical two-finger gripper on one arm and a custom-designed soft-robotics end-effector on the other one. This gripper is known as Universal Jamming Gripper (UJG) [1] and it resides in the category of *gripping by controlled stiffness*. One of the advantaged of the proposed approach, differently from the most adopted grippers which need a lot of hardware and software complexity, is that it uses a single actuation input. It exploits a simple suction-based grain-filled flexible ball. When pushed against an object, the granular mass wraps the object and

molds to its shape. The capability of granular material to pass from a malleable state to a rigid state constitutes the working principle. A novel perception algorithm determines the motion of the custom gripper. It is worth to notice that the algorithm does not need to use 3D reconstruction nor any AI tools for picking objects in a cluttered environment. It can detect the grasping point for an object without first recognizing it since it is agnostic to object identity. The proposed algorithm leverages only on the depth image taken from a single camera as input for identifying optimal grasping points.

Fig. 1: Working Setup

On the other way around, a state-of-the-art technique which searches in the point clouds for antipodal grasping points [2] controls the motion of the parallel-jaw gripper. Both arms are planned using the Moveit! framework which allows to bring the arm to the grasping point and placing the target to the desired position avoiding collision with the objects building an octomap of the environment.

An RGB-D camera, the Kinect v2, is installed in front of the head of the Baxter and at the same height pointing downwards for looking to the objects. Figure 1 depicts the working cell. With this setup, the camera has a clear view of the scene before the robot arm starts moving. While, due to the occlusion of the arm, when the robot is picking up the object, the camera is not able to check if the target is dropped or if it has been grabbed successfully. For this reason, the eye-in-hand cameras of the Baxter are used as gripping feedback. The end-effector approach for picking is always vertical to the target.

Fig. 2: Objects selected for the tests

Figure 2 depicts the adopted objects. They present different shapes, weights, material properties and are chosen with variable levels of difficulty trying to stress the potentiality of the vision algorithm and the custom gripper. It has been shown that the custom gripper can grasp securely most of the items for which at least one of the traditional grippers fails.

Vision algorithm

The algorithm takes as input the raw depth image from the Kinect v2 and outputs the target grasping point in the local frame of the camera. After a preprocessing phase of the input image, the algorithm starts an iteration. It filters on the depth saturating each pixel which has a value greater than an increasing threshold. On what remains visible, the algorithm searches for the edges or the corners of the objects. Among all the candidates the one with the lowest distance value from its closest contour that respects the area criterion is chosen. Of course, the gripper cannot pick up an object too heavy or too big, so it is convenient to filter out such objects. If any feasible grasping point is found, the threshold is increased allowing also objects with higher depth to be analyzed. The iteration stops when a grasping point is found or when there are no more graspable objects in the box. If both a corner and a line are found, the first is preferred because it ensures a better adhesion for the gripper.

III. RESULTS

Grasping tests to assess the capabilities of the custom gripper have been conducted picking up the objects shown in figure 2 in isolation. For each one, different configurations have been taken into account, resembling the possible displacements the object could assume in the clutter. Trials have been equally

distributed among the possible configurations, for a total of 30 attempts each.

Gripping force and grasping performance strongly depend on the picking point and the relative center of gravity of the objects and their surface material (mainly porous). When fails happen, the other end-effector is used trying to improve the performance of the overall system.

In addition, a comparative study of the algorithmic performance of the proposed method with respect to two of the state-of-the-art techniques has been conducted. One is the work of the MIT-Princeton team that won the first place for the stowing task in the Amazon Picking Challenge in 2017 [3]. The other is the approach used for controlling the parallel-jaw gripper [2]. For our tests, an Alienware x51 r2 with an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 960 graphics card has been employed. An Ubuntu 14.04 machine has been containerized, through *docker*, to run the ROS nodes which interact with the Baxter ROS master. It has been shown that the grasping success rate of the proposed work is competitive with the state-of-the-art systems just mentioned. Furthermore, the perception algorithm outperforms the other two approaches for the searching time of the grasping points. When a corner is detected, it takes just 0.003s to output the target point. With lines, the required time very depends on the configuration of the objects, ranging from 0.02s, when objects have almost the same depth, to 0.06s in the worst-case scenario, when the graspable objects have bigger depth with respect to the one that has the lowest depth but is not graspable.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a system able to grasp novel objects in a cluttered environment employing two different types of grippers and the corresponding vision systems. One of the end-effector is a custom-made Universal Jamming Gripper that, with its perception algorithm, shows a competitive grasping success rate and outperforms the other state-of-the-art systems taken as reference in the time spent to find grasping points.

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